

CardiomyoML: Classification of cardiomyopathies and prediction of new biomarkers with machine learning

January-February 2023

Fellowship of the MAGNet:

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Supplementary Information

Tables

Table S11. Description of the performance metrics to evaluate the machine learning models

Performance metric	Description	Formula
Accuracy	The number of correct predictions divided by the total number of predictions.	$ACC = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$
Precision	The ratio of true positives and total positives predicted.	$PR = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$
Recall	The ratio of true positives to all the positives in the ground truth.	$REC = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$
F1score	The harmonic mean of precision and recall.	$F1 = 2 \times \frac{PR \times REC}{PR + REC}$
Balanced accuracy	The average between the recall and the specificity. It measures the average accuracy obtained from both the minority and majority classes.	$BACC = \frac{REC + SPE}{2}$
MCC	It considers true and false positives and negatives and is generally regarded as a balanced measure that can be used even if the classes are of very different sizes. The MCC is in essence a correlation coefficient value between -1 and +1.	$MCC = \frac{TP \times TN - FP \times FN}{\sqrt{(TP + FP)(TP + FN)(TN + FP)(TN + FN)}}$
AUC-ROC	The AUC is the area under the ROC Curve. This area is the probability that a classifier will rank a randomly chosen positive instance higher than a randomly chosen negative one.	

TP = true positives; TN = true negatives; FP = false positives; FN = false negatives; MCC = Matthews correlation coefficient; ROC = receiver operating characteristic curve

Table S12. Performance metrics of all 25 classifiers employed in the binary classification task of *DCM versus NF* using the test data

Model	Accuracy	Balanced Accuracy	F1 Score	MCC	Precision	Recall
SGDC	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Calibrated CV	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Perceptron	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Passive Aggressive	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Logistic Regression	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Ada Boost	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.97	0.97	1.00
Linear Discriminant Analysis	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.97	0.97	1.00
Ridge CV	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.97	0.97	1.00
Ridge	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.97	0.97	1.00
Random Forest	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.97	0.97	1.00
Bagging	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.97	0.97	1.00
Linear SVC	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.97	0.97	1.00
Extra Trees	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.97	0.97	1.00
LGBM	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.97	0.97	1.00
K-Neighbors	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.94	0.94	1.00
Nu SVC	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.94	0.94	1.00
SVC	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.94	0.94	1.00
XGB	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.94	0.94	1.00
Extra Tree	0.94	0.94	0.94	0.88	0.91	0.97
Decision Tree	0.94	0.94	0.94	0.88	0.91	0.97
Gaussian NB	0.90	0.90	0.90	0.79	0.91	0.88
Bernoulli NB	0.87	0.87	0.87	0.73	0.83	0.91
Nearest Centroid	0.85	0.85	0.85	0.70	0.83	0.88
Quadratic Discriminant Analysis	0.61	0.61	0.61	0.23	0.59	0.67
Label Spreading	0.51	0.50	0.34	0.00	0.00	0.00
Label Propagation	0.51	0.50	0.34	0.00	0.00	0.00
Dummy	0.49	0.50	0.33	0.00	0.49	1.00

MCC = matthews correlation coefficient; SGDC = stochastic gradient descent classifier; CV = cross-validation; SVC = support vector classifier; LGBM = Light gradient-boosting machine; NB =naive bayes; XGB = Extreme Gradient Boosting

Table S13. Performance metrics of all 25 classifiers employed in the binary classification task of *HCM versus NF* using the test data

Model	Accuracy	Balanced Accuracy	F1 Score	MCC	Precision	Recall
Linear Discriminant Analysis	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
SGD	0.97	0.98	0.98	0.91	0.86	1.00
Perceptron	0.97	0.98	0.98	0.91	0.86	1.00
Linear SVC	0.95	0.97	0.95	0.84	0.75	1.00
Passive Aggressive	0.95	0.97	0.95	0.84	0.75	1.00
Ridge CV	0.97	0.92	0.97	0.90	1.00	0.83
Ridge	0.97	0.92	0.97	0.90	1.00	0.83
Logistic Regression	0.97	0.92	0.97	0.90	1.00	0.83
LGBM	0.97	0.92	0.97	0.90	1.00	0.83
Decision Tree	0.97	0.92	0.97	0.90	1.00	0.83
Gaussian NB	0.97	0.92	0.97	0.90	1.00	0.83
Bernoulli NB	0.97	0.92	0.97	0.90	1.00	0.83
Nearest Centroid	0.92	0.89	0.93	0.73	0.71	0.83
Ada Boost	0.95	0.83	0.94	0.79	1.00	0.67
XGB	0.95	0.83	0.94	0.79	1.00	0.67
Bagging	0.95	0.83	0.94	0.79	1.00	0.67
Extra Trees	0.95	0.83	0.94	0.79	1.00	0.67
SVC	0.95	0.83	0.94	0.79	1.00	0.67
Calibrated CV	0.95	0.83	0.94	0.79	1.00	0.67
Random Forest	0.95	0.83	0.94	0.79	1.00	0.67
K Neighbors	0.92	0.82	0.92	0.69	0.80	0.67
Extra Tree	0.77	0.66	0.79	0.27	0.33	0.50
Label Propagation	0.85	0.50	0.78	0.00	0.00	0.00
Label Spreading	0.85	0.50	0.78	0.00	0.00	0.00
Dummy	0.85	0.50	0.78	0.00	0.00	0.00
Quadratic Discriminant Analysis	0.28	0.44	0.32	-0.10	0.13	0.67

MCC = matthews correlation coefficient; SGDC = stochastic gradient descent classifier; CV = cross-validation; SVC = support vector classifier; LGBM = Light gradient-boosting machine; NB =naive bayes; XGB = Extreme Gradient Boosting

Table S14. Performance metrics of all 25 classifiers employed in the binary classification task of *PPCM versus NF* using the test data

Model	Accuracy	Balanced Accuracy	F1 Score	MCC	Precision	Recall
LGBM	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Linear Discriminant Analysis	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Ridge CV	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Ridge	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Logistic Regression	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Ada Boost	0.97	0.99	0.98	0.70	0.50	1.00
Bernoulli NB	0.97	0.99	0.98	0.70	0.50	1.00
Decision Tree	0.94	0.97	0.96	0.56	0.33	1.00
Nearest Centroid	0.91	0.96	0.94	0.48	0.25	1.00
SGD	0.77	0.88	0.85	0.29	0.11	1.00
Perceptron	0.77	0.88	0.85	0.29	0.11	1.00
Passive Aggressive	0.71	0.85	0.81	0.25	0.09	1.00
Linear SVC	0.71	0.85	0.81	0.25	0.09	1.00
Bagging	0.97	0.50	0.96	0.00	0.00	0.00
Dummy	0.97	0.50	0.96	0.00	0.00	0.00
Label Spreading	0.97	0.50	0.96	0.00	0.00	0.00
Extra Trees	0.97	0.50	0.96	0.00	0.00	0.00
Label Propagation	0.97	0.50	0.96	0.00	0.00	0.00
Random Forest	0.97	0.50	0.96	0.00	0.00	0.00
Calibrated CV	0.97	0.50	0.96	0.00	0.00	0.00
K Neighbors	0.97	0.50	0.96	0.00	0.00	0.00
Gaussian NB	0.97	0.50	0.96	0.00	0.00	0.00
SVC	0.97	0.50	0.96	0.00	0.00	0.00
XGB	0.97	0.50	0.96	0.00	0.00	0.00
Extra Tree	0.94	0.49	0.94	-0.03	0.00	0.00
Quadratic Discriminant Analysis	0.34	0.18	0.50	-0.22	0.00	0.00

MCC = matthews correlation coefficient; SGDC = stochastic gradient descent classifier; CV = cross-validation; SVC = support vector classifier; LGBM = Light gradient-boosting machine; NB =naive bayes; XGB = Extreme Gradient Boosting

Table S15. Performance metrics of the best ensemble classifiers employed in the multiclass classification task using the external dataset

	Random Forest	LGBM	XGB
Accuracy	0.51	0.53	0.48
Balanced accuracy	0.60	0.50	0.43
Precision	0.70	0.55	0.57
Recall	0.51	0.53	0.48
F1score	0.49	0.54	0.52
MCC	0.24	0.01	0.04

LGBM = Light gradient-boosting machine; XGB = Extreme Gradient Boosting; MCC = Matthews correlation coefficient

Figures

Figure S11. ROC curves of ensemble models performance in A. the binary classification task of HCM versus NF using test data B. the binary classification task of PPCM versus NF using test data. The ROC curves depict the balance between the false positives and the true positive rates. The upper left corner represents a perfect classifier, whereas the dashed line in the middle represents a random classifier. The area under the curve (AUC) is a numeric representation of the performance of the model.

Figure SI2. Venn diagram of the top 500 most important genes according to the best ensemble-based models for A) HCM B) PPCM and C) multi-class classification tasks

Figure SI3. Density plots of log transformed CPM values for gene expression in A) the MAGNet dataset B) the GSE55296 dataset C) the GSE116250 dataset and D) the GSE46224 dataset. Each line represents a different sample.

Figure S14. Principal component analysis scores plot for the MAGNet dataset along the first two principal components. Each point represents a different sample, colored by etiology according to the legend.

A) PCA (GSE46224 - unscaled)

B)

C)

Figure S15. Principal component analysis scores plot for the GSE46224 dataset prior to the scaling step along A) the first two principal components B) the first and third principal components and C) the second and third principal components. Each point represents a different sample, colored by etiology according to the legend.

Figure SI6. Principal component analysis scores plot for the GSE55296 dataset prior to the scaling step along A) the first two principal components B) the first and third principal components and C) the second and third principal components. Each point represents a different sample, colored by etiology according to the legend.

Figure SI7. Principal component analysis scores plot for the GSE116250 dataset prior to the scaling step along A) the first two principal components B) the first and third principal components and C) the second and third principal components. Each point represents a different sample, colored by etiology according to the legend.

Figure SI8. Principal component analysis scores plot for the GSE46224 dataset after the scaling step along A) the first two principal components B) the first and third principal components and C) the second and third principal components. Each point represents a different sample, colored by etiology according to the legend.

Figure SI9. Principal component analysis scores plot for the GSE55296 dataset after the scaling step along A) the first two principal components B) the first and third principal components and C) the second and third principal components. Each point represents a different sample, colored by etiology according to the legend.

Figure SI10. Principal component analysis scores plot for the GSE116250 dataset after the scaling step along A) the first two principal components B) the first and third principal components and C) the second and third principal components. Each point represents a different sample, colored by etiology according to the legend.